

A Critical Analysis of "Hijacking limitations of working memory load to test for composition in language"

by Christy, Riyan

The paper in question is a study by Ullman, Bulut, and Walenski. Using the locus of the English language, Ullman et al. (2024) hypothesize that people will perform worse when working with regular word forms than they will with irregular forms. The researchers are expanding upon the Words and Rules theory, which perhaps is best presented by Pinker (1999) in his book *Words and Rules*. According to this theory, regular forms -- forms that follow a fixed rule (e.g. walk: walked) -- are composed/decomposed. That is, regular-form words are composed when they are produced, and decomposed when they are apprehended. In contrast, each irregular form -- e.g. dig: dug -- are memorized as a whole word instead of being broken apart. The theoretical question of Ullman et al. is clear: do regular forms tax an individual's working memory more than irregular forms? To investigate this construct question, their empirical question is, in a 3-back production task, will subjects perform worse with regular forms or irregulars? Ullman et al. predict that in this task regulars will be harder to work with than irregulars, leading to worse performance with regulars.

The 3-back production task is a task where the participant is asked to give the third word back. That is, in this experiment, each participant is given a word on a computer screen, which stays for 1500 milliseconds. Then a fixation cross appears and initiates a timer terminated by the participant's oral response. The participant is to say out loud the third word back in the sequence, the first back being the word just presented prior to the fixation cross. So if "a", "b", "c" were

given in that order and then a fixation cross appears, they need to give "a". To ensure they do not tire and hence affect experiment's findings, participants are given a break of a few minutes after each sub-list.

The experiment is within-subjects, and the participants are probably college students. Ullman et al. do not say whether their participants are college students, but the researchers report they tested forty-six native English speakers with a mean age of 21.4 years ($SD = 5.2$) and a mean of 14.5 years of education ($SD = 1.7$). Looking at both the age and the years of education, I think it is likely that most of the participants are college students.

The researchers measure the participants' performance among the percentage of correct responses on the 3-back task. Among the correct responses, the researchers also recorded each response's reaction time. (They also measured covariates to control for confounds.)

The results see the subjects get more correct on the irregular forms than they do with the regulars. And among the correct items, the subjects perform faster on the irregulars than they do with the regulars.

These findings support their hypothesis that people perform worse on regulars than they do with irregulars. If regular and irregular forms make the same demand on working memory, we would expect the performance to be roughly similar. So the answer to the empirical question suggests an answer to the researchers' theoretical question: regular forms do tax the working memory more than irregulars do. Moreover, the findings provide more evidence for the Word and Rules theory the researchers build on. In addition, this evidence is not explained by competing theories, such as those that say both regulars and irregulars are stored as whole words, or others

that say both regulars and irregulars are (de)composed.

Although competing theories do not provide plausible alternative explanations, and the researchers have guarded against confounds (by measuring covariates), their method -- the n-back test -- is only one working memory paradigm. There are other paradigms, and some researchers (Miller et al, 2009) question whether the n-back is a valid measure of working memory. As such, it is still unknown whether their hypothesis holds when examined under other working memory paradigms.

References

- Miller, K. M., Price, C. C., Okun, M. S., Montijo, H., & Bowers, D. (2009). Is the N-back task a valid neuropsychological measure for assessing working memory? *Archives of Clinical Neuropsychology*, 24(7). <https://doi.org/10.1093/arclin/acp063>
- Pinker, S. (1999). *Words and rules: The ingredients of language*. Basic Books.
- Ullman, M. T., Bulut, T., & Walenski, M. (2024). Hijacking limitations of working memory load to test for composition in language. *Cognition*, 251, 105875. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cognition.2024.105875>